

REVIEW: HOW CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AFFECTS TO BUSINESS VALUE

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ОБЗОР: КАК КОРПОРАТИВНОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ВЛИЯЕТ НА СТОИМОСТЬ БИЗНЕСА

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Abstract

This article discusses the issue of the impact of corporate governance on the value of a business. As you know, corporate governance is represented by several principles of its implementation in specific organizations. And the analysis of the impact of corporate governance on business value should be viewed through the prism of these principles. Compliance or non-compliance with the principles of corporate governance affects the economic performance of the company, such as the valuation of shares, the ability to attract capital, which is considered one of the important factors for business development.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассмотрен вопрос о влиянии корпоративного управления на стоимость бизнеса. Как известно, корпоративное управление, представляется несколькими принципами его реализации в конкретных организациях. А анализ влияния корпоративного управления на стоимость бизнеса следует рассматривать через призму этих принципов. Соблюдение или несоблюдение принципов корпоративного управления влияет на экономические показатели компании, таких как оценку стоимости акций, на способность привлекательности капитала, который считаются одним из важных факторов для развития бизнеса.

Keywords: business, corporate governance, value, financial statement, investment.

Ключевые слова: бизнес, корпоративное управление, стоимость, финансовая отчетность, инвестиции.

Introduction.

In international practice, it is generally accepted that a business is an economic entity that carries out certain commercial activities [1]. The value of a business is higher than the value of an enterprise as a property complex by the amount of so-called intangible assets that are inseparable from the human potential of the organization.

Theoretical aspects of research work.

In the works of the classics of political economy (U.Petty, A.Smith, D.Ricardo, K.Marx) presents the concept of the labor theory of value, where value is considered as a measure of reified labor. In the works of marginalists (L.Walras, O.Boehm-Bawerk, etc.), value is represented as a measure of the utility of a thing. A.Marshall [2] proves that value depends on many factors.

In professional valuation activities, the value, first of all, determines the measure of utility. The value is determined by their "marginal utility" based on subjective assessments of human needs. Also, the cost reflects the measure of labor costs and the relative rarity. From an economic point of view, value is the estimated cost of specific goods and services at a particular time in accordance with the chosen interpretation of value. There are several types of costs that are specified in international, European, and Russian valuation standards. The main types of costs are those specified in International Financial Reporting Standards:

- market value.
- investment value.

- liquidation value;
- cadastral value.

In determining the value of shares and businesses, only three types of value can be used: market value, investment value and liquidation value; cadastral value cannot be used for the purpose of evaluating the entire property complex or business, since it is determined only in relation to real estate.

Let's consider approaches and methods to estimating the value of an evaluation object. The analysis of the concepts of "approach" and "method" to the evaluation of objects of evaluation as a whole is presented in IFRS, which states that the approach to evaluation is a set of evaluation methods united by a common methodology.

Below are the approaches to valuation, as well as the conditions for their application in the formation of business value [3]:

Revenue approach-it is assumed that the value of the object being evaluated is determined by its ability to generate revenue streams in the future.

Comparative approach - It is based on comparing the object of valuation with similar businesses that are similar to each other in various characteristics (for example, economic, technical, etc.), about which the transaction price is known.

Cost approach-the appraiser determines the value of the valuation object based on the value of assets owned by the business organization and liabilities assumed.

Naturally, each approach uses different assessment methods. Most often, the revenue approach is used to estimate the business value.

It should be noted that currently, according to IFRS, when determining the value of an object of assessment within the framework of applying each of the assessment methods used, the appraiser must establish and justify the need to make adjustments used in calculations and their amount. That is, premiums and discounts for control and liquidity are applied not only in the comparative approach, but also in all approaches used, if the object of valuation is not 100% ownership.

Net asset method

And in the comparative approach, the need to apply such adjustments is dictated by the methodology of applying comparative approach methods: in the transaction method, this is necessary, since the information received from the market has the result of different levels of control over the sold analogues; in the capital market method, information on analogues from the stock market always has the price of a non-controlling interest (since shares in uncontrolled packages).

In the cost approach, there are two estimation methods:

Picture #1. Two valuation methods in the cost approach [4]

At the same time, it should be noted that within the framework of applying each valuation method, the value of the entire business is determined at once (100% of the business ownership share), and only then the cost of not 100% of the ownership share is calculated if the share is the object of valuation. And at this stage, there is a need to apply premiums and discounts for control and liquidity. As noted above, such premiums and discounts are applied in the case of estimating the value of less than 100% of the business ownership interest when all valuation approaches are applied. At the same time, the amount of bonuses and discounts for control depends on the size of the estimated share - the larger the share of business ownership, the higher the premium. This is due to the set of rights of the owner of the corresponding share [5].

Methodological aspects of research work.

The main document that defines the methodology for assessing the value of a business in practice, IFRS defines the value of a business as "the monetary expression of economic benefits from the entrepreneurial activity of an organization", that is, based on the application, first of all, of a profitable approach to valuation. At the same time, monetary benefits from entrepreneurial activity are the cash flows of an organization formed within the framework of three types of its activities: operating, investment, and financial. Within the financial

(cost) model of decision-making, business value is a criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of decisions made by the organization's management. Business value is the goal of an organization's long-term financial policy [6].

Historically, the criteria for the effectiveness of an organization's activities were financial indicators.

Currently, one of the most well-known classifications of factors affecting the value of a business is their division into financial and non-financial, including the impact of corporate governance.

The analysis of financial indicators is based on accounting data, and financial and information meters are based on monetary indicators.

In the process of financial analysis, the following indicators are evaluated [7]:

- changes in the most important absolute indicators of the organization.
- dynamics of the company's relative performance indicators;
- market stability, liquidity and solvency of the company;
- efficiency of using own and borrowed capital;
- efficiency of capital advance payments.

The main objective of financial indicators is to demonstrate the state of the company's business in

terms of value and values and their correlation. They include basic and derived indicators that are financial in nature and / or use monetary values as a unit of measurement. Their application is an important part of the traditional way of conducting and managing an organization's business, the traditional model of managerial decision-making. The accounting management model is not effective enough in terms of evaluating and managing business value. And not all traditional financial ratios have a significant relationship with the price and value of the business [8]: only indicators of the capital structure and profitability have significant relationships.

The most effective financial decision-making model is considered to be based on the concept of value-based management (VBM) [9].

Non-financial performance indicators of an organization include [10]:

- ✚ personnel indicators (evaluation criteria, for example, are working conditions, staff turnover, etc.);
- ✚ indicators for the production of material resources (for example, the volume of output, etc.);
- ✚ indicators for the consumption and use of material resources (for example, order size, etc.).
- ✚ indicators of the management system (evaluation criteria, for example, are the number of divisions, the number of levels of the management hierarchy, and so on).

In the work of I.Y. Belyaeva and M.M. Pukhova, non-financial indicators include image and business reputation [11].

Traditional financial statements do not contain the necessary information about corporate governance, environmental protection, the quality of interaction with customers and suppliers, that is, about the socio-environmental aspects of doing business that underlie the concept of sustainable development. Traditional financial statements contain only financial indicators of the company's activities, which was one of the reasons for the development of non-financial (corporate social) reporting [12].

Analyzes and results of research work.

Trends in the development of modern corporate reporting are aimed at combining financial and non-financial reporting under the complex name "integrated reporting", which is currently one of the main areas of effective organization management [13] and provides a list of non-financial indicators of organizations' activities.

Indicators of integrated reporting depending on the industry affiliation of the organization, the objects of research for which were organizations from such industries as oil and gas; energy; metallurgy and mining; production of machinery and equipment; chemical, petrochemical, perfume; woodworking, pulp and paper; production of food and other consumer goods; telecommunications; finance and insurance; housing and public utilities; cement production and construction; education, healthcare; transport; retail; other types of services.

Thus, depending on the company's industry affiliation and the type of its non-financial reporting, various non-financial indicators are distinguished. The most

common ones are compliance with regulatory documents and standards; respect for human rights; labor protection; environmental impact; emissions and waste levels; corporate social responsibility; built trusting relationships with all stakeholders of the organization; training and professional development of the company's employees; health protection of the organization's employees and consumers.

When assessing the value of a business, it is quite common to divide indicators into fundamental and non-fundamental ones. The origins of this classification come from the concept of fundamental business value. As you know, fundamental analysis is based on the forecast of income indicators from the investment object. When assessing the value of a business, this is reduced to applying the discounted cash flow method in a revenue approach and applying the concept of value-based management (VBM) [14].

The division of indicators into fundamental and non-fundamental factors was analyzed, for example, in the works of authors P.Y. Staryuk [15], V.E. Udaltsov and others. At the same time, P.Y. Staryuk divides fundamental factors into four groups of revenue, profitability, dividend payments and industry variables and asserts that internal indicators can be equated with financial ones because they have an impact on the value of the organization.

However, the work of I.V. Kosorukova and a team of authors under her editorship [16] indicates that traditional indicators of financial analysis, such as liquidity, solvency and turnover, do not affect the value and capitalization level (price) of public joint-stock companies. At the same time, it was proved that the cost and capitalization level of indicators of the capital structure and return on sales, equity and assets are affected. Consequently, not all financial indicators can be called fundamental factors of business value. At the same time, it should be noted that despite the fact that a group of corporate governance indicators is reflected in the non-financial statements of companies, the study by I.V. Kosorukova and N.N. Prokimnov proved the influence of some significant facts on changes in the share prices of organizations. That is, corporate governance is a fundamental factor.

At the same time, we consider it incorrect to identify financial and fundamental factors, so it is necessary to distinguish groups of indicators in relation to the business value:

- 1) Financial and non-financial assets.
- 2) Fundamental and non-fundamental.

Modern scientific literature actively analyzes corporate governance factors that affect the value of a business.

Thus, P.Y. Staryuk, in addition to fundamental factors, singled out corporate governance as a factor that determines the ability of an organization to make management decisions that are close to the ideal environment, and the presence of errors in making such decisions is justified solely by external uncontrolled factors [15]. Within the framework of corporate governance, he identified external and internal variables that have an impact on the value of the business.

The Corporate Governance Code is an essential tool for managing the activities of joint-stock companies, which indicates the need to determine the relationship between the principles of the Code and the value and level of capitalization of organizations.

Thus, the analysis allows us to identify the following factors related to the principles of corporate governance, which will be used for correlation and regression analysis: capital structure, availability of state participation, choice of field of activity, dividends paid, elements of business reputation, revenue, profitability indicators, material facts.

Conclusion.

In valuation activities, the value of an object of valuation is determined using income, comparative and cost approaches. Each approach uses different methods in the process of evaluating the value of a business. Evaluation approaches and methods have their own advantages and disadvantages. The main method of estimating the value of a business is the discounted cash flow method within the income approach.

There are several types of costs. In assessing the value of shares and businesses under Russian law, only three types of value can be used, namely: market value, investment value and liquidation value.

The analysis allows us to identify the following factors related to the principles of corporate governance that will be used for correlation and regression analysis in this paper: capital structure, availability of state participation, choice of field of activity (industry), dividends paid, elements of business reputation, revenue, profitability indicators, material facts.

References

1. Оценочная деятельность: учебник/коллектив авторов; под ред. И.В. Косоруковой. – Москва: КНОРУС, 2021. – 334 с. – ISBN978-5-406-06897-7.
2. Marshall. Principles of Economics. – 1890. – 8th ed. – 627 p.
3. Пузыня, Н.Ю., Мягков, В.Н., Барин, Н.П., Булаевская, Е.С., Ванзонак, Д.А., Вовк, А.С., Красильников, Д.С., Стабровская, К.Ю., Егорова, А.К., Григорьев, И.В., Маринич, Д.А., Кубрак, Д.Н., Киршина, Н.Р., Шведова, Н.Ю., Мамедли, О., Сахновская, О.Е. Оценка собственности в условиях волатильности и трансформации рыночных условий: монография/ под ред. Н. Ю. Пузыня. – Санкт-Петербург : Санкт-Петербургский государственный экономический университет, 2021. – 170 с. – ISBN 978-5-7310-5549-9.
4. Федотова, М. А., Булычева, Г. В., Евстафьева, Е. М. Оценка пакетов акций предприятий: поправки на контроль и ликвидность. – Москва: Финакадемия, 2008. – 103 с.- ISBN 978-5-7942-0584-8.
5. Шеннон, П. П. Оценка бизнеса. Скидки и премии. Пер. с англ. – Москва: Маросейка, 2011. – 413 с. – ISBN 978-5-903271-76-4.

6. Екимова, К.В. Финансовая политика компании: учебное пособие / Екимова К.В., Громова Е.И., Кери И.Т. – Москва: КноРус, 2020. – 330 с.

7. Ионова, А. Ф., Селезнева, Н. Н. Финансовый анализ: учеб. 2-е изд. – Москва: Проспект, 2009. – 624 с. – ISBN978-5-392-00501-7.

8. Совершенствование критериев принятия решений на базе стоимостно-ориентированного менеджмента как основа роста конкурентоспособности экономики России. Монография / Под ред. И.В.Косоруковой / И.В.Косорукова, Н.В.Мирзоян, Н.А.Бондарева, А.Ю.Родин, М.А.Шуклина, И.А.Ягодкина. – Москва: Университет «Синергия», 2019. – 206 с.

9. Теплова, Т.В. Корпоративные финансы: учебник и практикум для академического бакалавриата / Т.В.Теплова. – Москва: Издательство Юрайт, 2013. – 655 с. (С. 162-165)

10. Ширяев, Е.Г. Роль нефинансовых показателей деятельности в оптимизации бизнес-процессов предприятия // Управление и финансы. – 2010. – № 2. – С. 115. (С. 115)

11. Беляева, И.Ю., Пухова, М.М. Интеграция корпоративной социальной ответственности в систему корпоративного управления в России // Экономические системы. – 2017. – Т. 10, – № 2 (37). – С. 20–23.

12. Мирзоева, Е. В. Нефинансовая отчетность как источник информации о деятельности компании // Международный бухгалтерский учет. – 2014. – № 22 (316). – С. 25–37.

13. Усанов, А.Ю., Мощенко, О.В. Интегрированная отчетность как инструмент корпоративного управления компанией // Проблемы теории и практики управления. – 2019. – № 5. – С. 103–108.

14. Бухвалов, А.В., Бандалок, О.В., Березинец, И.В., Волков, Д.Л., Гаранина, Т.А., Ильина, Ю.Б. Корпоративное управление: вопросы практики и оценки российских компаний: монография. – Санкт-Петербург: Изд-во «Высшая школа менеджмента», 2012. – 328 с. (С. 159)

15. Старюк, П. Ю. Влияние корпоративного управления на стоимость российских компаний: эмпирический анализ: специальность 08.00.10 «Финансы, денежное обращение и кредит»: диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата экономических наук / Старюк Павел Юрьевич; Государственный университет Высшая школа экономики. – Москва, 2008. – 184 с.

16. Совершенствование критериев принятия решений на базе стоимостно ориентированного менеджмента как основа роста конкурентоспособности экономики России. Монография / Под ред. И.В.Косоруковой / И.В.Косорукова, Н.В.Мирзоян, Н.А.Бондарева, А.Ю.Родин, М.А.Шуклина, И.А.Ягодкина. – Москва: Университет «Синергия», 2019. – 206 с. – ISBN 978-5-4257-0396-5.